

THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC

A turning point in the lives of
Nigerians

MUOKA CHIBUZOR GOSPEL

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He has written several articles in various areas of life, many of which were published online and have earned accolades, rewards, and certifications.

In 2017, his NYSC essay submission to the Bible Society of Nigeria (BSN), which was centred on the "INCORRUPTIBLE JUDICIARY AS A CATALYST FOR AN EQUITABLE AND PROGRESSIVE SOCIETY" made it to the best six nationwide.

In 2019, his essay on "THE MENANCE - CHILD ABUSE" submitted to Abia State University Medical Students Association (ABSUMSA) was the best in the entire faculty.

He desires to continuously be involved in research and creative writings, so as to create positive impacts that contribute to the finding of lasting solutions that pacify the enormous problems of mankind, for a better tomorrow and a peaceful co-existence.

He also has serious commitments in lighting electronics, as he has devoted some of his spare time to learning and repairing lighting gadgets such as rechargeable lamps. This led to the Muokagram initiative (www.muokagram.com), which is geared towards helping to lift African households from the devastating impacts of poor power supply.

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the pre-existing conditions in Nigeria before the pandemic, assesses the profound impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Nigerians during the outbreak, and explores the anticipated transformations in the post-pandemic era. While Nigerians have faced various disease outbreaks in the past, none have left such a lasting mark as the battle against the Coronavirus. Life in Nigeria before the pandemic was challenging for many, but the sudden emergence of the virus became a harsh reality that disrupted the lives and aspirations of countless individuals. In response, the Nigerian government implemented stringent measures aligned with the World Health Organization's guidelines to curb the spread of the virus. Unfortunately, these efforts were marred by corruption within the government and healthcare sector. Nevertheless, a dedicated few worked tirelessly to counter the negative impact of corruption and restore humanity's dignity. Amid the chaos, as some succumbed to a predatory lifestyle driven by necessity and others grappled with perplexing conspiracy theories, many adapted to new ways of life to mitigate the pandemic's adverse effects. The post-pandemic period is expected to usher in a new normal, reflecting a significant societal transformation. This demonstrates that the Nigerian society has reached a pivotal juncture, having undergone a comprehensive evolution in the wake of the pandemic.

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Abbreviations:

COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2
FMoH	Federal ministry of health
NCDC	Nigerian Centre for Disease Control
WHO	World Health Organization
HIV/AIDS	Human Immunodeficiency Virus/ Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome
NYSC	National Youth Service Corps
NFA	Nigerian Football Association
JAMB	Joint Admission and Matriculation Board
WAEC	West African Examination Council
NECO	National Examination Council
FEC	Federal Executive Council
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
5G	Fifth-Generation wireless
INEC	Independent National Electoral Commission
NIREC	Nigerian Interreligious Council
CAN	Chrstian Association of Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

"Out of difficulties grow miracles."
- Jean de La Bruyère

The **Coronavirus Disease 2019** (COVID-19) emerged in 2019, resembling the mythical monster, Medusa, with its many heads – a formidable pandemic. Similar to its historical counterparts, the Bubonic Plague (known as the Black Death) and the Spanish Flu, anyone it encountered embarked on a perilous journey towards the grave. The name "Coronavirus" was derived from the crown-like projections visible on the virus's surface when observed under a microscope. In Latin, "*Corona*" translates to "Crown."

The news of its deadly nature and the absence of any known cure spread like wildfire, causing the entire world to tremble with profound fear. Just like a frightened child watching an apocalyptic horror film for the first time, the world hastily sought safety by staying indoors. During these moments of solitude, people's minds were consumed with thoughts of the most effective strategies to combat the spread of the novel COVID-19 disease, which is caused by the infectious viral strain known as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2).

The outbreak of the disease was believed to have originated in a large animal and seafood market in Wuhan city, Hubei province, China. The rapid spread of the virus from China across Asia, Europe, America, the Middle East, and Africa, along with the rising death toll among numerous infected individuals, was seemingly unthinkable. This led the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare COVID-19 a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. It became abundantly clear that the greatest wealth is indeed one's health, as the absence of it left every aspect of human life vulnerable to devastation.

THE PRE-PANDEMIC PERIOD IN NIGERIA

Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa and the 7th largest in the world, is home to over 190 million people. Demographic studies reveal that nearly 42.54% of the Nigerian population is under the age of 14. In recent times, Nigeria has stood out as the Giant of Africa due to its vast human resources and robust economy.

The country proved to be fertile ground for new businesses, commercial agriculture, and technological advancements. Several factors contributed to this, including less stringent regulations, low-income taxes, the low levels of natural disasters, a low crime rate, and a large, skilled workforce that could also be consumers. People could thrive by earning a daily income from even small ventures. Regrettably, this democratic giant has been plagued by corruption, ethnocentrism, xenocentrism, tribalism, nepotism, and religious intolerance.

These instabilities are rooted in a lack of unity, which has emboldened the scourge of corruption, the true enemy of national development, since the country's independence in 1960. Nigeria ranks as the world's 8th largest crude oil exporter, but corruption has deprived many Nigerians of the benefits of this valuable resource, leaving them in poverty, illiteracy, and unemployment. A significant amount of infrastructure remains in disrepair, and sectors like healthcare, power, and education have not been spared the ravages of corruption.

Soon, the return of Africans from the diaspora, particularly Nigerians, began in earnest, driven by the fear of contracting COVID-19 in foreign lands. Those at home, who had been hearing about COVID-19, dreaded their return, as they were viewed as potential carriers. Although the rejection of returnees seemed inhumane, the possibility of introducing the virus from those returning was a legitimate concern.

Many Africans faced a difficult choice and, after consultations, it was concluded that *"the one who loves you, loves you with your flaws and intends to do something about it."* Consequently, returnees were welcomed after being quarantined in isolation centers or advised to self-quarantine for at least 14 days, allowing for health assessments to ensure they did not exhibit classical signs of the disease, which include indiscriminate coughing or sneezing, fatigue, anosmia (loss of smell), ageusia (loss of taste), high fever, pneumonia, and severe respiratory distress. COVID-19's initial symptoms often mimicked those of malaria.

The state of Nigeria's healthcare sector is in shambles, as evidenced by World Bank statistics in 2018 estimating the average life expectancy of Nigerians to be only 54.49 years.

This low life expectancy underscores significant public health challenges, including the HIV/AIDS epidemic, high child and maternal mortality, tuberculosis, polio, and malaria. The advent of COVID-19 has further decreased the life expectancy of Nigerians.

Despite the desire for positive change in governance among the impoverished masses, some politicians appeared indifferent to the nation's problems, preferring to seek healthcare and education abroad due to the dire state of their homeland. However, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic marked a turning point in the lives of all Nigerians.

"All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others." This proclamation was made by the pigs who controlled the government in George Orwell's novel, "Animal Farm." Yet, in the face of a microscopic virus, the laws of Animal Farm no longer held sway. People from all walks of life, whether rich or poor, were now equals. The idea of seeking refuge in foreign lands lost its appeal, as everyone was reminded of the significance of having a secure and safe home – Nigeria.

2019 Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19)

This illness can be mild. However, in some cases it is severe enough to require hospitalization. If you have been to mainland China within 14 days and are experiencing these symptoms, seek medical care immediately and tell your healthcare provider about your symptoms and travel.

Who is at risk?

- Recent travelers from mainland China. This does not include Taiwan, Unit 8 Assessment - Google Drive Macau, or Hong Kong.
- Individuals with close contact to a person with COVID-19.
- Current risk to the general public is low.

How is it spread?

- Through the air after coughing or sneezing.
- Close personal contact with an infected person.
- Touching an object that has the virus on it, then touching your mouth, nose, or eyes.

What are the symptoms?

- Fever
- Cough
- Shortness of breath

Symptoms may appear in as few as 2 days or as long as 14 days after exposure.

To prevent illness:

- Wash your hands often.
- Avoid contact with people who are sick.
- Avoid touching your mouth, nose, or eyes.

THE PANDEMIC PERIOD IN NIGERIA

On February 14, 2020, the virus was confirmed to have reached Africa, with the first case recorded in Egypt. By February 27, 2020, the virus was confirmed in Nigeria, when an Italian citizen in Lagos tested positive. Thus, the battle against the virus began in Nigeria. Many Nigerians who are not inquisitive historians, may never have heard about the era of the Bubonic plague (1346-1353) and Spanish flu (1918-1920).

This was because of the absence of the scientific revolution during those periods, coupled with the fact that everyone was busy talking about the First World War (1914-1918), and the general lack of interest in studying history among modern-day Nigerian students. The possibility of anything like the Bubonic plague and Spanish flu occurring in this modern era, was a dream any young Nigerian would confidently bet to never come true. But here we are today, a disease called COVID-19 has rendered mankind powerless, and made many dust old books and browse the internet to read about the events that took place during the Bubonic plague and Spanish flu, and how our ancestors adopted social distancing and other measures amid lack of scientific advancements to contain the then-unknown causative agents.

In response to the invasion of COVID-19 in Nigerian society, the Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) and the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) took swift preventive actions, with support from the government and masses, following the World Health Organization (WHO) directives, to be able to establish COVID-19 screening centers, and detect infected patients for immediate isolation and treatment. There was a formidable alliance formed between the NCDC and the telecommunication companies, mass media and social media firms, and Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to ensure that every Nigerian was well informed about the disease symptoms, its prevention, and its route of infection.

The urgency in action was because when the outbreak first occurred in China, the WHO did not hesitate to enlist Nigeria as being among the African countries with a highest-risk for the viral infection. The NCDC adopted medical protocols for patient observation, screening, detection, contact tracing, isolation, and treatment, to be able to contain the virus. Additionally, the government enforced national lockdowns, social distancing, hand washing, face masks usage, and hand sanitizers as preventive measures.

Rumors were spreading faster than the virus and the government worked to reassure the citizens of its readiness to adopt every measure necessary to curtail the spread of the virus. It was also realized that modern-day improved transportation system was a strong agent of the

virus dispersal. Thus, in April 2020, the Nigerian government ordered the lockdown of the nation, believing that if the transport system was stopped and human to human contacts was reduced, the virus would be contained.

With immediate effect, the Nigerian airlines cancelled all flights; the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme suspended their orientation exercise, the Nigerian Football Association (NFA) suspended all football activities, the Actors Guild of Nigeria banned movie sets across the nation, examination bodies (JAMB, WAEC, NECO) suspended activities, the Nigerian railway corporation and land transport companies were shut down, interstate borders closed, all courts were closed, schools of all levels were shutdown, major markets were closed, a ban was placed on weddings, burials, seminars, conferences, religious gatherings, and any other large gatherings of more than twenty persons.

Even the Federal Executive Council (FEC) meeting was suspended indefinitely. Indeed, the lockdown became a reality as everyone was forced to stay at home, and whoever violated the law could suffer a great deal. People became rare and a deep silence was everywhere. Just then, it appeared as if an enemy had successfully laid a siege on the highly anticipated visions expected to be accomplished in the year 2020.

However, to avoid the extinguishment of life as the prolonged lockdown began to breed contempt, the government approved that only vehicles carrying food items, medicals, pharmaceuticals, and petroleum supplies were allowed on Nigerian roads. Also, providers of essential services like agricultural products sellers, security providers, healthcare providers, drug stores, electricity companies, fire services, essential departments of banks, media houses and telecommunication companies were exempted from the sit at home order.

Unfortunately, the lockdown of all public places and the retirement of people to their homes led to the lay-off of workers, as most private companies were unable to generate enough revenue to keep paying the workers. The COVID-19 pandemic brought untold financial crisis and unprecedented backwardness to the Nigerian economy, and Nigerians likened it to moving from frying pan (the pre-pandemic period) to fire (the pandemic period).

Who knows what the post-pandemic period would look like? Many asked this question because it was obvious that it would not be business as usual after the lockdown. Most parents found it extremely difficult to make a living and provide for themselves and family.

Mr Essien a cab driver and a father of six children was heard complaining to his neighbors, *“I am not bothered about myself catching the virus, am only worried about my*

family dying of hunger. Am going straight to the streets to find food for my family. I don't care what the government will do." As he spoke angrily, his kind neighbors could only calm him down by giving him some tubers of yam and assuring him of the soonest end of the lockdown.

According to Medscape reviews, the COVID-19 related deaths in China have mostly involved elderly persons of greater than 60 years old and persons with any underlying health conditions. In full awareness of this fact, concerns arose about the mass urban-rural migration, as many decided to return to farming, and this may impair the idea of contact tracing and increase the possibility of infected persons, transmitting the virus to unsuspecting older relatives with weaker immune systems due to old age.

Moreover, Nigeria's sizable youth population, yearning for an active lifestyle, turned to books, movies, and the internet as an escape from the clutches of boredom. However, some young individuals, who failed to make the most of their time, succumbed to the inevitable allure of youthful exuberance, confirming the age-old adage, "An idle mind is the devil's workshop."

The frustration knew no bounds, manifesting in many families as a result of meager or nonexistent income, stringent spending, the psychological torment of excessive bank debit alerts, food shortages, and a lack of essential amenities, especially electricity. Also was the fear of the virus and the blurry future of uncertainty which tormented the people. Thus, the masses called out to the government and well-to-do Nigerians for palliatives and pleaded with the government for the relaxation of the stringent measures put in place for the sake of safety.

In response to the plea of the masses, a significant amount of aid in the form of food and money was contributed by both governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as affluent individuals. However, it became evident that the distribution of these palliatives was inefficient and insufficient, as unscrupulous elements in charge of the distribution hoarded them in warehouses.

As a result, the intended impact of the palliatives was severely diminished, leaving the masses to fend for themselves. In this challenging environment, some individuals resorted to exploiting those who were most vulnerable among them, starting with price hikes on essential commodities, particularly food price.

This unfortunate turn of events awakened the presence of predatory individuals within society, reminiscent of Shakespearean cut-throat profiteers, as they sought to capitalize on the misfortunes and mistakes of others. Shockingly, even some security agents devolved into

becoming bandits, engaging in attacks and extortion at the slightest provocation in exchange for money. These unpatriotic actions resulted in the tragic and premature deaths of many young individuals.

At this critical juncture, it seemed as if Darwin's theory of evolution had come to life, with the battle for survival intensifying. Charles Darwin's words echoed, "It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change." Undoubtedly, the COVID-19 pandemic ushered in numerous unacceptable changes, pushing society to the brink of anarchy. The suffering had become unbearable, and the fabrics which held the society together were falling apart.

Unmasking Corruption: A Pandemic within the Pandemic in Nigeria

Perhaps, Nigerians might have coped better if COVID-19 were the sole challenge they faced. It became apparent that a pervasive behavioral disease, often termed "corruption," had spread more rampantly than the virus itself. The urgent need for "transparency" as a form of treatment became undeniable. The presence of corruption within the Nigerian government and the healthcare sector was a far cry from the aspirations of the nation's founding fathers.

As Patricia J. Garcia, a Peruvian physician and former Minister of Health in Peru (2016-2017), aptly put it, *"Although there is no comprehensive, universally agreed definition of corruption, corruption is the abuse of entrusted power for private gains."* This corruption in Nigeria, particularly within the healthcare sector, severely hindered the effective management of COVID-19. It stemmed from a lack of resilience, accountability, and integrity.

In certain states of the country, the failure of the government to recognize the dedication of health workers by increasing their risk allowances resulted in reduced motivation among healthcare professionals to provide their best services. The inadequate distribution of palliatives, both in the form of food and money, further complicated the situation. While some individuals benefited, others found themselves in dire straits, resorting to criminal activities such as armed robbery, pickpocketing, shoplifting, and various forms of scams to make ends meet.

During the battle against COVID-19, various forms of corruption emerged within the healthcare sector, significantly impeding the fight against the virus. The first form of corruption was absenteeism, with several physicians and healthcare workers abandoning their posts and neglecting the use of provided personal protective equipment (PPE). This negligence had dire consequences, as some patients perished from non-COVID-19 related ailments. These patients,

who arrived at the hospital coughing and in respiratory distress, might have suffered from conditions like asthma attacks or other respiratory disorders.

At this juncture, one can't help but wonder about the essence of the Hippocratic Oath, and whether its solemn pledge, *"to dedicate my life to the service of humanity; the health and well-being of my patient will be my first consideration,"* had been forgotten. The second form of corruption manifested as the embezzlement and theft of funds, as well as the illicit sale of government supplies such as face masks, hand sanitizers, and hand washing buckets in the market at allegedly reasonable prices. This opportunistic profiteering meant that people had to pay for items that were meant to be distributed free of charge.

The third form of corruption involved the manipulation of data, leading many Nigerians to doubt the authenticity of the reported COVID-19 cases. The alteration of data appeared to be motivated by self-interest, aiming to secure more supplies, earn extra productivity incentives, and avoid being labeled as unproductive. Unfortunately, this manipulation rendered COVID-19 data in Nigeria unreliable, disrupted public health statistics, and hampered the efficient distribution of palliatives.

Conspiracy Theories amidst COVID-19: Faith, Fear, and Folly

The proliferation of conspiracy theories during the pandemic period led to confusion and blame being directed in various directions, with disastrous consequences in many societies. Firstly, there was the theory of the avenging God, which gained traction in a deeply religious nation like Nigeria. Many believed that the deaths caused by the Coronavirus were a form of divine punishment for those who had disobeyed God. It was believed that only those who didn't adhere to their religious doctrines would contract the virus.

Secondly, the theory of ongoing biological warfare was widely contemplated. Some believed that the virus had been intentionally created in a laboratory for the purpose of economic sabotage against prosperous nations, with the intent to bring them down.

Thirdly, there were notions of unconventional treatment plans for fighting the disease. Some believed that consuming alcohol could cure the virus, leading to tragic consequences such as people mistakenly drinking methanol, resulting in over 700 deaths in Iran. Others believed that residing in a very hot environment was a remedy, while some thought that excessive consumption of the drug hydroxychloroquine or the intravenous injection of bleach (sodium hypochlorite) could cure the virus. Many Nigerians lost their lives due to these unconventional and often dangerous treatment plans, including the use of strange herbal

concoctions.

Lastly, there was the theory linking 5G radiation to COVID-19. It was claimed that the disease had originated in a 5G smart city in China. This theory incited arson attacks in the United Kingdom, with over 50 cell towers supporting 5G networks being targeted. In response, many Nigerians expressed vehement opposition to the installation of a 5G network in Nigeria. However, the World Health Organization (WHO) addressed these conspiracy theories, clarifying that they were falsehoods. The WHO urged people to seek answers from qualified health experts and maintain optimism about a COVID-19 vaccine that would ultimately protect them from the infection and bring an end to the disease.

From Crisis to Hope: Nigeria's Fight against COVID-19

However, amid the tough times in the lives of Nigerians, as many mourned their loved ones who died due to the virus, interventions came from philanthropists and religious organizations, who went around the country feeding the people and giving them enormous words of encouragement, so that they would understand that no condition was permanent. Their kindness was the utmost act of love for humanity. It was like a cup of water to a thirsty man in a desert; and thus, he was motivated to be hopeful. The role of religion was indispensable as the Nigerian Interreligious Council (NIREC) urged Christians and Muslims in the country to pray against COVID-19 which was a common concern.

To avoid the virus spread, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) directed churches nationwide to adopt the conduction of online church services for the citizens. This idea also fostered the continuity of the Educational sector as teachers took the opportunity to teach their students who would access the classes via the internet, radio and television devices. Amazingly, several Nigerian Professors, Scientists, and Herbalists were not relentless in finding a solution (a cure or vaccine) for the pandemic. Along the line, Madagascar an East African country surfaced with a herbal remedy called COVID-Organics.

Although the herbal remedy did not secure the approval of the WHO and the Western world due to the absence of proper pre-clinical and clinical trials, which are essential in drug development, it received endorsements and requests from fellow African states. This was met with visible joy from Nigerians, who praised the commendable efforts that contributed to fighting the deadly plague. This demonstrated that Africans are not passive observers of problems and are willing to take action rather than wait for intervention from world powers.

Despite Western recommendations regarding the use of Hydroxychloroquine in COVID-19 treatment, Africans have proactively sought alternative solutions to the problem. Currently, a majority of Nigerian scientists are deeply engaged in rigorous research to combat the pandemic. On June 16, 2020, the WHO promptly confirmed that Dexamethasone, a potent anti-inflammatory drug, could potentially save the lives of patients who were critically ill with COVID-19. Notably, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) made commendable efforts in sensitizing the entire population through bulk SMS messages, reaching people with active SIM cards, about the importance of wearing face masks, using hand sanitizers, and practicing social distancing. By utilizing SMS primarily, they effectively dispelled the conspiracy theories surrounding the nature of the COVID-19 disease.

On March 2, 2021, Nigeria received its first shipment of four million doses of the Oxford-AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine from the COVAX initiative at Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport. Dr. Cyprian Ngong, a physician at the National Hospital in Abuja, became the first person in Nigeria to receive a COVID-19 vaccine on March 5. President Muhammadu Buhari also received his first COVID-19 vaccine dose on March 6. Additionally, on March 21, Nigeria received an extra 300,000 doses of the Oxford-AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine from MTN.

Figure 1 President Muhammadu Buhari receives the COVID-19 vaccine

By the end of March 2021, approximately 0.7 million vaccine doses had been administered. As of the end of April 2022, an impressive 38.4 million vaccine doses had been administered, and 14.9 million individuals had been fully vaccinated, having received both the first and second dose of the vaccine.

The Roll out Schedule for COVID-19 vaccine in Nigeria as at 2021. Source: Wikipedia

Phase	Priority group	Progress
1	Health workers and supporting staff, frontline workers and first responders	In progress
2	Priority 1: Persons aged 60 years and above. Priority 2: Persons aged 50–59 years	
3	Persons aged 18–49 years with co-morbidities	
4	The rest of the eligible population aged 18–49 years	

THE POST-PANDEMIC PERIOD IN NIGERIA: THE POSSIBILITIES

"In times of change, learners inherit the earth, while the learned find themselves beautifully equipped to deal with a world that no longer exists."

— Eric Hoffer

According to George Bernard Shaw, an Irish playwright, *"progress is impossible without change, and those who cannot change their minds cannot change anything."* At this juncture, it would not be out of place to say that the COVID-19 pandemic has indeed transformed the dynamics in Nigeria. The Nigerian populace is evolving tremendously, as the winds of change shaped minds and left many in contemplation about the way forward in the post-pandemic period.

Due to the disorganized nature of the lockdown in its early stages, it was only natural for many to struggle to think outside the box. Most people could only see calamity, but a few had the foresight to embrace the silver lining amidst the dark clouds. However, as the lockdown persisted, people were compelled to adapt and change. There was a growing willingness to learn new ways of doing things, especially embracing remote work and technology. The era of technophobia and cyberphobia began to recede, giving way to a new way of life driven by adaptation. The COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst for significant changes in various sectors in Nigeria, including business (e-commerce), education, agriculture, health, and politics.

Firstly, in the business sector, the pandemic resulted in widespread job losses as many companies struggled to pay their employees due to reduced revenue. This impact was especially pronounced in the aviation and banking industries, leading to a surge in unemployment rates in Nigeria. In response, many employees transitioned to businesses that could be managed remotely from their homes. What initially served as an alternative, buying and selling over the internet (e-commerce), became the preferred method of conducting transactions. It is anticipated that the shift towards e-commerce, along with the skills and knowledge gained during the pandemic, will continue to shape the post-pandemic business landscape.

Secondly, the educational sector faced a significant setback, particularly in terms of its academic calendar, as students were forced to stay home with school closures. There was a legitimate concern that students might not engage in academic work during this period,

potentially leading to distractions that could hinder their return to school post-pandemic. To counteract these challenges, e-learning platforms that leveraged social and mass media channels emerged as a viable solution. Fortunately, many teachers and students embraced this new approach. It is expected that in the post-pandemic period, educational institutions will readily incorporate more e-learning techniques into their curriculum, allowing educators to teach remotely when physical presence is not possible due to unforeseen circumstances.

Thirdly, the agricultural sector, which has historically been a cornerstone of the Nigerian economy, accounting for a significant portion of non-oil exports and employing approximately 70% of the country's workforce, witnessed a decline in interest since the 1970s oil boom. As the allure of oil production grew, many abandoned traditional agricultural practices. This shift led to rural-urban migration and food shortages in the nation, as urban dwellers favored imported food products over locally grown options. The neglect of agriculture was further exacerbated by government apathy and the export of Nigerian agricultural products by the elite during times of food scarcity.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic reversed this trend by prompting urban-rural migration, causing a decline in Nigerian oil prices (as the demand for crude export collapses), reducing food import and export, and increasing people's awareness of the value of agriculture in times of adversity. It is expected that in the post-pandemic era, many will recognize the importance of diversifying their income streams, acknowledging that it is easier to lose a white-collar job than a farmland that guarantees food, a fundamental necessity for human survival.

Fourthly, the healthcare sector emerged as the bastion against the formidable disease. It demonstrated its vital role in safeguarding humanity through the unwavering dedication of healthcare professionals. Nigerians now recognize the pressing need for well-equipped domestic hospitals, as unforeseen calamities such as the COVID-19 pandemic could deprive even the affluent of access to foreign healthcare services if developed nations close their borders to immigrants from developing countries.

This crisis underscored the importance of prioritizing healthcare at home, and Nigerian leaders have gained a heightened awareness of the adage that "health is wealth." In response to the pandemic, the renovation and enhancement of hospitals were initiated, and it is anticipated that Nigerian healthcare facilities will undergo substantial improvements, with the acquisition of advanced medical equipment and a greater number of qualified healthcare professionals in the post-pandemic era, as the potential for future pandemics cannot be dismissed.

Finally, the political sector bore the brunt of the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to the suspension of executive, legislative, and judicial activities—the three main branches of government—in various countries worldwide. The pandemic's impact on Nigerian politics was marked by prominent politicians' deaths and isolations, often making headlines. Notably, the virus claimed the life of Abba Kyari, the Chief of Staff to the President of Nigeria, and several governors, statesmen, and stateswomen were isolated after testing positive for COVID-19.

The outlook for political elections in Nigeria during both the pandemic and post-pandemic periods appears uncertain, as numerous challenges are anticipated. Many individuals may be hesitant to approach politicians, participate in political gatherings, engage in door-to-door campaigning, join public marches, or attend large-scale rallies due to the social distancing measures adopted during the pandemic. These factors could necessitate the rescheduling of elections in a democratic nation like Nigeria. The lingering memory of the alleged COVID-19 death of Burundian President Pierre Nkurunziza during political elections for his successor remains a significant deterrent for many elites contemplating political involvement.

It is expected that new strategies will be embraced to ensure the political sector's survival. This may involve political parties heavily investing in technological protocols for human-to-human connections, with technological platforms becoming a substitute for face-to-face interactions. Additionally, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), which oversees elections in Nigeria, may recognize the need to adopt remote e-voting systems. This would enable citizens to cast their votes anywhere and at any time via computers and internet-connected devices, aiming to mitigate the negative effects of social distancing and historical irregularities in Nigerian elections. Such changes would ideally promote greater acceptance of election results by both voters and candidates.

CONCLUSION

Indeed, the COVID-19 pandemic has inflicted unforgettable hardships on the lives of many Nigerians, Africans, and the entire world. While we mourn the loss of loved ones to this disease, we must acknowledge the profound changes that have reshaped every aspect of Nigerian society during the transition from the pre-pandemic period to the pandemic and now to the post-pandemic era. The exacerbation of corruption only intensified the pandemic's devastating impact, but the honesty and compassion of a few individuals proved to be life-saving.

This period should serve as a lesson, inspiring every Nigerian to become paragons of virtue and embrace new, healthier lifestyles, much as they did during the pandemic. A healthy lifestyle can enhance life expectancy, and good deeds will always prevail over evil. Nigerians should not remain as inflexible as trees but should be adaptable, seizing opportunities in the face of adversity.

The COVID-19 pandemic will eventually become a story of the past, much like the Bubonic plague and the Spanish flu. However, our solemn duty as humanity is to draw lessons from the past (pre-pandemic period) and the present (pandemic period) to ensure a progressive future (post-pandemic period). We must learn from our history to avoid repeating past mistakes. When we stand together, we can confront challenges as vast as the ocean and as towering as the sky.

Contributors

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